

REVIEW OF PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIAL PROBLEMS

June 2016, Vol. 3, No.2: (1-14)

ISSN 1596-1550

ADOLESCENTS' DRUG USE/ADDICTION AND SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT PATTERN IN NORTHERN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Dr. Paulina M. Anake

Department of Educational Foundations,
Guidance and Counseling
University of Calabar, Calabar
p.mhua@yahoo.com +2348034839236

ABSTRACT

The consumption of hard drugs has drastically increased among teenagers between the ages of 14-30 (both males and females) with high risk effect. Substance such as alcohol, cannabis, amphetamines among others are now been taken frequently and in large quantities-by youths. This study is aimed at investigating the influence of adolescents' drug use/addiction on social adjustment problem in Ogoja Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the main objective of this study one null hypothesis was formulated in four dimensions of adolescents' social adjustment A sample of 627 students were randomly selected, using stratified and simple random sampling techniques. A one way analysis of variance (ANO VA) was used for statistical analysis at .05 level of significance. The result of the findings revealed that adolescents' drug use/addiction significantly influence their social adjustment with respect to coping with peer pressure, school rule, academic pressure and adult/societal expectations. Based on the results and findings it recommended that,

preventive measures that involve parents, teenagers, school, communities, media and law enforcement agency should be put in place to help reduce drug use/addiction and assist the youth in their social interactions with others.

KEYWORDS: Adolescent, Drug Use/Addiction, Social Adjustment

INTRODUCTION

Social adjustment is the achievement of balance in social relationships usually aided by the appropriate applications of social skills in one's environment. It is the psychological process through which individual's strive to cope with daily challenges in attempting to satisfy their, physical, social and personality needs, seeking affection, trying to achieve mastery of vocation and striving for independence. Adjustment therefore becomes necessary for an adolescent to cope with his/her physical and social environment. Adjustment is a process of altering behavior to reach a harmonious relationship with the environment. It is a process of change and search by an individual for some level of balance or acceptance with the environment, others or oneself (Bier, 2008).

Adolescence is a period of dramatic challenge that requires adjustment to changes in the self, family, school and peer group. For both boys and girls the period is marked largely by social changes, adolescents must cope with a large and even changing peer pressure, developmental[!] peer relationships becomes quite integral and assume greater value in shaping and understanding the self. The individual develop diverse needs that can be satisfied by distinctive social interactions at the different phase of development (Erdley, Nangle, Newman & Carpenter, 2001). Social adjustment among adolescent is therefore affected by family, environment (society involve), parent-child relationship, peer relation, school pressure and academic pressure.

Similarly adolescents and adults are always on the go, attempting to reach the goals which will reduce tensions created by their needs. It -is important for the teachers and parents to recognize that every activity of the child (adolescent) satisfies some need. Hence whenever a child is restless, aggressive, impudent, cooperative, delinquent, he/she is making an adjustment to life. During this adjustment period, emotions which appear include sadness and loss, uncertainty and anxiety and worry that one will not be adequately adjust in the new culture or setting. The result is tiredness or may not eat or sleep well; which affect the adjustment domain in his /her ability to cope, adapt and adjust to the ebb and flow of events in one's day to day lives.

With the complexity of our society, adolescents are increasingly cut off from the activities of their elders (adult), leaving most young people with education as their sole occupation and have prolonged their adolescence. The adolescent years have become marked by violence to an alarming degree. The phenomenon of teenage suicide, drug abuse and addiction, sexuality and early pregnancy, school drop-out, poor performance in school and risk taking behavior of many sorts have become particularly disturbing. All the

adolescents want is to have fun and be in control.

The adolescents socially are not aware of the consequences of all these practices and have a hard time listening to their parents (elders). The period is often a lonely one. The adolescent always feels a failure because he/she believes that he has matched up to a personal ideal, that his successes are often felt by him to be temporary. He may experience guilt and worry because he believes that what he thinks or does is not normal or that he has transgressed against what he considers acceptable or because he prefers to remain a child (Obianu, 2008). Some feel not only lonely, but confused and isolated, uncertain as to whether they need be worried about their behavior or their thoughts. They feel depressed and frustrated.

Furthermore, the adolescent interactions and moves from dependence on his parents towards emotional independence; make him feels his thoughts and feelings are his own, and no longer the reactions of parents without necessarily feeling that he must give in to them. He/she feels changing relationships with his parents means giving up his childhood attachment, seeking new forms of satisfaction and new kind of friends. At the same time he feels he has lost his parents and alone (Berger, 2011). As a result of all these, young people start taking drugs because they are looking for the pleasure which these substances give, the reward comes when they feel the desired effects, the wish to continue in the state; or to experience the pleasure again is what pushes the user or addict to look for more drugs and to remain in the addiction cycle. Some adolescents try drugs out of curiosity or due to peer pressure, while others take drugs because they are offered. With continuous use they acquire the habit or the custom of taking them. The nervous connections which intervene in the behavior reinforce themselves. In this way, the habit begins to form part of their daily life.

According to Boob and Kreek (2007), drug addiction is a pathological or abnormal condition which arises due to frequent drug use. The disorder of addiction involves the progression of acute drug use to the development of drug-seeking behavior, the vulnerability to relapse, and the decreased slowed ability to respond to naturally rewarding stimuli. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV) has categorized three stages of addiction: preoccupation/anticipation, binge/intoxication, and withdrawal/ negative effect. These stages are characterized respectively, everywhere by constant cravings and preoccupation with obtaining the substance, using more of the substance than necessary to experience the intoxicating effects, and experiencing tolerance, withdrawal symptoms and decreased motivation for normal life activities.

Similarly, addiction is a chronic often relapsing brain disease that causes compulsive drug seeking and use, despite harmful consequences to the addicted individual and to those around him or her. Although the initial decision to take drugs is voluntary for most adolescents (people), the brain changes that occur over time challenge an addicted person's self-control and hamper his or her ability to resist internal impulses to take drugs. The other consequences of drug use/addiction include, mental disorder (insanity), disease - lung diseases, poverty, school dropout, poor performance, accidents, armed robbery, stealing, fraud, liver cirrhosis, respiratory

infections, loss of appetite, social outcast in relationship with others and family becomes ineffective and disrupted; which may finally lead to death or poor communication with others affecting their social interactions with peers, friends and family members (Isah & Limbeabe, 2015).

Drug use/addiction also increases the rate of crimes; people indulge in stealing, snatching of bags, GSM phones, kidnapping for ransom, 419, killing and related anti-social behaviors. It also increases the number of unemployed youths, and decreasing the societal labor force or manpower; and paints the country's image both locally and internationally bad and dangerous. This calls for an urgent need for counseling approaches which help to create awareness and re-orientation to youth and society on the effects of drug use and addiction. There is a need to enact stringent laws against drug use. Parents and adults should act as models for the child. The daily behavior of parents in the family, their conversation and interactions, actions and reactions, their agreement and disagreement, their values and norms forms the basis of adolescents socialization which help to a great extent solve their problem of adjustment.

Based on this premise the study was carried out to determine the influence of adolescent drug use/addiction on social adjustment pattern in Ogoja Education Zone of Cross River State, with the view of providing empirically validated data to guide adolescents, parents, government of Nigeria, and Cross River State in particular, social workers and counselors on the national and rehabilitation strategies for the adolescent child drug use/addiction.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the theory of Erik H. Erikson's development theory (1963). He takes a more social view of personality development and stresses the unique psychological tasks of adolescence. He places more emphasis on the influence of sociological processes on the behavior of the individual; and takes a closer look on the role the family and society plays in the development of the individual and pays particular attention to the adolescent's identity. Erikson (1963) describes this stage of development as comprising identity vs identity diffusion. He further asserts that the period of adolescence is marked by conflicts that are mainly related to that of identity. Adolescent struggle between internal urges and environmental demands to help build and confirm a reasonable stable identify.

According to the theory, "identities" can be shaped and reshaped throughout life time; good parenting and conducive interacting environment can produce the tool for this achievement. Hence for healthy growth and development of the adolescent a resolution with strength, morals and virtues is needed for self-socialization and adjustment. He also identify that each stage of development involves what he called a "crisis" in personality; which requires the balancing of a positive tendency to a corresponding negative one. This resolution equips the adolescent with "virtue" or strength for the next stage of development. This theory is relevant to this work on the basis that it reshapes the personality of the developing child and provides him/her with virtue and strength to maintain good relationship with others and re-adjusts to

the normative principles of the society.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Behavioral pattern in the family and society has affected the length of hours or interactions between children and parents. Parents who are expected to be good models for personality excellence are rather more interested in self-pursuit to the detriment of caring for their children. Hence individual differences exist in physical appearance, temperament, intelligence, abilities and aptitudes. This has thrown adolescents into many antisocial practices such as get rich syndrome, stealing, disobedience, lying, aggression, cheating, gangsterism, kidnapping and use of illicit substance to change mood. It tends to indicate that such behaviors have become embedded in our system as features of life for the contemporary Nigerian adolescent. The danger about this situation is that they invariably pave way for further behavioral maladjustment which poses threat to the child, school and society. Hence the researchers are motivated in this study to identify relevant variables of adolescents drug use/addiction and their social adjustment in its four dimensions of coping with peer pressure, school rules, academic pressure and adult/societal expectations; which is transferred to adolescents drug use/addiction behavior, misconduct and conflict with self, parents, school and society.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study was to examine the influence of adolescent's drug use/addiction and social adjustment in senior secondary school students (SSII) in Ogoja Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study was to investigate whether adolescents' drug use/addiction has any influence on their social adjustment. One research question was formulated:

To what extent does adolescents' drug use/addiction influence their social adjustment?

To achieve the objective of this study one null hypothesis was formulated:

Adolescent's drug use/addiction does not significantly influence their social adjustment. It was assumed that adolescents' drug use/addiction and social adjustment problem changes with his psychological environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Related literatures would be review on the views, opinions, assertions and empirical findings of earlier studies on adolescent's drug use/addiction and social adjustment. The review literature is organized under: adolescents' drug use/addiction and social adjustment. Drug contains chemicals that tap into the brain's communication system and disrupt the way nerve cells normally send, receive and process information. There are at least two ways

that drugs cause this disruption: (1) by initiating the brain's natural chemical messengers and, by over stimulating the "reward circuit" of the brain. Some drugs, for example marijuana and heroin, have similar chemical messengers called neurotransmitters, which are produced by the brain. This similarity allows the drug to "fool" the brain's receptors and activate nerve cells to send abnormal messages. Also other drugs, such as cocaine or methamphetamine, can cause the nerve cell to release abnormally large amount of natural neurotransmitter, which is needed to shut off the signaling between neurons (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2004).

Hence, drug creates addiction. Addiction deprives users of their freedom of action. They attack the brains, lungs, liver, the centre of all vital functions. Drugs make the organism develop tolerance; create high physical and psychological dependency; alcohol affect the liver and heart, while tobacco damage the lungs. It wakes up latent mental disorder. The fastest and easiest road to teenage child's ruin is drug use and addiction. Any chemical substance, whether of natural and synthetic origin which is used to alter perception, mood, or other psychological states, affect the individual. Adolescents do not believe the effect of drug used. Many are simply unaware of the dangers and damages to health, which may lead to disorders such as depression and memory loss.

The United Nation Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2004) reported that illicit drugs seized in 2013 by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) weighted 339,968kg with an estimated street value of 34 million naira. The breakdown is as follows: cannabis 205,373kg, psychotropic substances 133,920kg, methamphetamine 340.8kg and cocaine 290.2kg. Others are heroin 24.53kg, amphetamine 19.297 and ephedrine 0.28 grammes. In 2013 alone, a total of 3,271 drug dependent persons were successfully counseled in NDLEA facilities nationwide. This comprises of 3,062 males and 209 females. Additional 802 treated cases were reported by hospital and other drug dependence treatment centres in Nigeria. From the report Nigeria was rated highest in cannabis seizure in Africa, and remains the country with the highest seizure of cannabis in the region followed by Egypt. It was also reported that cannabis is the most prominent drug in offences for possession for personal use. With regards to trafficking offence, amphetamine type stimulant (ATS) is prominent in Asia and cocaine in the Americas.

Furthermore, UNODC representative Marian Sissoko stated that this year's World Drug Report shows that "around 243 million people aged 15-64 consumed an illicit drug in 2012. Out of this number, problem drug users, those who have most difficulties with drug consumption account for around 27 million or 1 in every 200 people". The report exposed a gap in the treatment of drug abuse as only 1 in 6 drug users around the world receive the drug dependence treatment they need. This invariably means so many users and addicts are victims of crimes, with concomitant negative impact on health, public safety, productivity and governance. Also the cost of drug prevention and treatment globally is very high estimated at \$35 billion dollars. Hence drug use and addiction affect the emotional and social adjustment of the individual, also decreasing the economic productivity of the country as attention are focus on how to help the addict.

Aliyu (2014) stated that, it is most heart-rending to know that there are tons of drugs in circulation which are either adulterated or have old NAFDAC numbers, or expired, but are still being consumed by ignorant and unsuspecting members of the public. Another dimension to drug abuse is that most youths take them to help boost their immune system, but this ultimately causes damage to their bodies.

Addiction to drugs/substances can be emotional, psychological, biochemical dependent or a combination of the three. Users who are psychologically dependent feel that they need drug in order to feel good about themselves whereas those who are emotionally dependent need increasingly larger doses of drugs in order to achieve the initial effects and will suffer from withdrawal symptoms when they stop. She further affirmed that cannabis and Indian hemp are the most frequently -used and abused drug in Nigeria, followed by amphetamine and to a lesser extent heroin and cocaine. Organic solvents are also becoming increasingly popular especially among street people and adolescents. While long distance drivers and some law enforcement agents believe that narcotics will increase their energy level for long and tedious hours. Hence, anxiety, frustration and economic depression, unemployment and social deprivation are among the many reasons linked to the drug use and -addiction.

Afolabi, Ayilara, Akinyemi and Oia-Olurun (2013) in their survey of drug use among young people in Ife, Nigeria, found that students most widely use caffeine (19.8%), alcohol (5.6%), cigarette (6.3%) and occasionally marijuana (0.4%) as psychoactive substances. The substances were obtained from open drug market (23.5%), peers (5.2%) and village drug hawkers (0.8%). Reasons for drug use included to keep awake (22.2%), to experience high feeling (21.8%), for body building (14.1%) and to moderate appetite (11.9%). The drugs were used by oral route of administration mostly and there was a high frequency of psychotropic drug use among students with caffeine being the most widely used. Drug use by the youth could be attributed to psychosocial perceptions of self need and peer influence. From the results, drug use by adolescents in school was highly influenced by peer group influence as a way to feel a sense of belongings, coming of age and self-independence.

Furthermore, Lynskey, Health, Buctiolz, Slutske, Madden, Nelson, Statham and Martin (2003) observed that, young people who smoke, drink or use marijuana often associate with peers who introduce them to harder drugs as they grow older. Marijuana not only tends to lead to hard drug use, but can be harmful in itself. Long term heavy use can impair memory and attention. Contrary to popular impression, adolescents do seem to care about what parents think. Adolescents who believe their parents disapprove of smoking are less likely to smoke (Surgent & Dalton, 2001). While rational discussions with parents can counteract harmful media influences and discourage or limit drinking in adolescents (Austin, Pinkleton & Fujioka, 2000). Hence, there is need for parents intervention to help, because the resulting effect in the frequency of drug use and addiction are many - car crashed, hand gun deaths, suicide, reflecting a violent culture in this age as well as adolescents' inexperience and immaturity, which often lead to risk taking and

carelessness.

In Cross River State, Nigeria, drug use/addiction has caused so much harm on the adolescent child leading to behavior disorder and misconduct and all forms of anti-social problems of adjustment in youth. There is no shortage of antisocial behaviors among them, such as fighting, bullying, hurting others, abusing other children with little or no concentration on learning. They display all forms of maladjusted behavior and find it difficult to conform to school rules and regulations, resulting in their poor performance and drop out. They also find it extremely hard to socialize and adjust to common norms and values at home, school and society; as a result feel lonely, isolated, dejected, depressed and think death or suicide the only way out.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted was ex-post facto. The targeted population consisted of all adolescents in Cross River State. The accessible population for the study consisted of all students in senior secondary schools in Ogoja Education Zone, Cross River State. The stratified and simple random sampling technique was adopted. To select the subject a 17% of 3,682 senior secondary school students {SSII} was used, with a sample .size of 627 students selected for the study. The research instrument was the questionnaire which comprises twenty (20) items, all of the Likert-type 4 point scale. The respondents were required to indicate their level of agreement for each statement. The questionnaire items were validated by experts in guidance and counseling, psychological, social work department and educational measurement, research and evaluation, affirmed that the entire instrument was suitable for measuring what it was purported to measure. The reliability index was found at 0.87. Through the assistance of a research person, the questionnaire administered were all retrieved and properly compiled.

RESULT

Hypothesis one

Adolescents' drug use/addiction does not significantly influence their social adjustment. The independent variable is adolescents' drug use/addiction, while the dependent variable is adolescent's social adjustment which had four dimensions in this study. Adolescents in the sample were categorized into three groups based on their scores on the drug use/addiction sub-variable as follows: (a) Below the mean-low level of drug use/addiction (b) About the mean-moderate level, of drug use/addiction (c) Above mean-high level of drug use/addiction. The statistical analysis technique deployed to test the hypothesis was one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The result is presented in table 1.

TABLE 1
Analysis of variance of the influence of adolescents' drug use/addiction on their social adjustment

Social adjustment sub-variable	Drug use/addiction	n	Mean	SD		
Coping with peer pressure	1 (Low Level)	167	9.53	1.47		
	2 (Moderate level)	335	7.87	1.15		
	3 (High Level)	125	8.35	0.28		
	Total	627	7.26	1.34		
Coping with school rule	1 (Low Level)	167	7.03	1.10		
	2 (Moderate level)	335	7.02	0.22		
	3 (High Level)	125	7.09	0.13		
	Total	627	7.81	0.60		
Coping with academic pressure	1 (Low Level)	167	9.07	1.19		
	2 (Moderate level)	335	8.98	1.66		
	3 (High Level)	125	8.72	2.05		
	Total	627	8.53	1.72		
Coping with adult/soc exp	1 (Low Level)	167	5.70	2.24		
	2 (Moderate level)	335	6.99	2.41		
	3 (High Level)	125	6.71	4.02		
	Total	627		3.01		
Social adj sub-variable	Source of variation	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F-value	Sig Level
Coping with peer pressure	Between group	320.336	2	160.168	123.456	.000
	Within group	809.562	624	1.297		
	Total	1129.898	626			
Coping with school rule	Between group	6.463	2	3.252	9.228	.000
	Within group	218.535	624	0.350		
	Total	224.398	626			
Coping with academic pressure	Between group	186.579	2	93.290	34.807	.000
	Within group	1672.454	624	2.680		
	Total	1859.033	626			
Coping with adult/soc exp	Between group	906.024	2	453.012	59.218	.000
	Within group	4773.564	624	7.650		
	Total	5679.588	626			

.05; critical F, 624 = 3.02

The sizes, means and SDs for the three groups of respondents on each of the four social adjustment sub-variables are shown in the upper part of Table 1. The actual results of ANOVA are shown in the lower part of the table. The table shows that the comparison of the three mean values on each of the social adjustment sub-variables yielded calculated F - ratios of 123.456, 9.228, 34.807 and 59.218 for social adjustment sub-variable of coping with peer pressure, coping with school rule, coping with academic pressure and coping with adult/societal expectations respectively.

Each of these F - ratios is greater than the critical F-ratio of 3.02 at .05 level of significant with 2 and 624 degrees of freedom. With these results the null hypothesis is rejected in each of the four instances. This implies that the level of

adolescents' drug use/addiction has a significant influence on adolescent social adjustment in all the four dimensions of. coping with peer pressure, coping with school rule, coping with academic pressure and coping with adult societal expectations. To further understand the pattern of the significant influence of adolescents' drug use/addiction on each of the four dimensions of social adjustment, a post hoc multiple comparison analysis was carried out using Fishers' least significant difference (LSD) test on each of the significant ratios. The result of this analysis is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Fishers' least significant difference (LSD) analysis of the influence of adolescents' drug use/addiction on their social adjustment

Soc adj sub-variable use/addiction (i (I J))	Level of drug (j) "	"	Mean difference Level	Standard	Sig.
Coping with P.P	Low	Moderate	1.658	.108	.000
		High	1.479	.135	.000
	Moderate	Low	1.,658	.108	,000
		High	0.179	.119	.134
	High	Low	1.479	.135	.000
		High	0.179	.119	.134
Coping with s.r	Low	Moderate	0.225	.056	.000
		High	0.2-41	.070	.134
	Moderate	Low	0.225	.056	.000
		High	0.017	.062	.001
	High	Low	0.241	.070	.000
		High	0.017	.062	.000
Coping with a p	Low	Moderate	1.257	.155	.000
		High	1.162	.194	.577
	Moderate	Low	1.257	.155	.000
		High	0.096	.172	.577
	High	Low	1.162	.194	.000
		High	0.096	.172	.577
Coping with adult/soc exp	Low	Moderate	0.831	.262	.000
		High	1.535	.327	.000
	Moderate	Low	2.831	.262	.000
		High	1.296	.290	.000
	High	Low	1.535	.327	.000
		High	1.296	.290	.000

Mean different is significant at .05 level

The results of analysis presented in Table 2 indicated that:

- i) For coping with peer pressure, adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction are significantly more adjusted than both adolescents with moderate level of drug use/addiction and adolescents with high level of drug use/addiction: Mean different between low level and moderate level (1.658), and between low level and high level (1.479) are each significant at .05 level, in other words, adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction cope much more with peer pressure than their counterpart with either moderate level or high level of drug use/addiction.
- ii) For coping with school rules, entries in Table 2 indicated that adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction are significantly more adjusted than those with both moderate level and high level of drug use/addiction. Mean different between low level and moderate level (0.225), and between low level and high level (0.24) are each significant at .05 levels. In other words, adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction cope much more with school rules than their counterparts with either moderate level or high level of drug use/addiction.
- iii) For coping with academic pressure, the results show that adolescents with moderate level of drug use/addiction, and those with high level of drug use/addiction are significantly more adjusted than their colleagues with low level of drug use/addiction. Mean different between moderate level and low level (1.257), and between high level and low level (1.162) are each significant at .05 levels. In other words, adolescents with moderate level of drug use/addiction cope much more with academic pressure than their counterparts with low level of drug use/addiction.
- iv) For coping with adult/societal expectation, Table 2 shows that adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction are significantly more adjusted than adolescents with both moderate level and high level of drug use/addiction. Mean different between low level and moderate level (2.831), and between low level and high level (1.535) are each significant at .05 level in other words, adolescents with low level of drug use/addiction cope much more with adult/societal expectations than adolescents with either moderate level or high level of drug use/addiction.

Generally, and in answer to research question 4, the level of drug use/addiction by adolescents has a significant influence in their social adjustment in all the four dimensions. The lower the level of drug use/addiction, the higher the level of their social adjustment (except in the case of coping with academic pressure where the reverse in the case).

DISCUSSION

The result of the hypothesis revealed that adolescents¹ drug use/addiction has a significant influence on their social adjustment in terms of the four sub-variables. The findings from the results was in line with the report of the United Nation's Office on Drugs and Crime (UNDDC) (2014), that illicit drug seized in 2013 by NDLEA weighted 339,968kg with an estimated street value of N34 billion naira. The breakdown is as cannabis 205,373kg, psychotropic substances 133,920kg, methamphetamine 340.8kg and cocaine 290.2kg. Others are heroin 24.53kg, amphetamine 19.297 and ephedrine 0.28 grammes, In2013alone, a total of 3,271 drug dependent persons were successfully counseled in NDLEA facilities nationwide. This comprises of 3,062 males and 209 females. Additional 802 treated cases were reported by hospital and other drug dependence treatment centres in Nigeria. From the report Nigeria was rated highest in cannabis seizure in Africa, and remains the country with the highest seizure of cannabis in the region followed by Egypt. Also it was reported that, cannabis is the most prominent drug in offences for possession for personal use. Hence, drug use/addiction affect the adolescents' emotional and social interaction with others, making it difficult for an addict to adjust easily to normal life.

Similarly, the result from the findings is also in agreement with the findings of Afolabi et al (2012) in their survey found that drug use among young people in Ife, Nigeria, reported that students most widely used caffeine (19.8%), alcohol (5.6%), cigarette (6.3%) and occasionally marijuana (0.4%) as psychoactive substances. The substances were obtained from open drug market (23.5%), peers (5.2%) and village drug hawkers (0.6%). Reasons for drug use included to keep awake (22.2%), to experience high feeling (21.8%), for body building (14.1%) and to moderate appetite (11.9%). The drug were mostly any time and mainly by oral route of administration. There was a high frequency of psychotropic drug use among the students with caffeine being the most widely used. Drug use by the youth could be attributed to psychosocial perceptions of self need and peer influence. From the results drug use by adolescents in school was highly influenced by peers, reasons to feel belongings, high and independence, and societal influence through illegal sale of drugs and usage.

Gibbs (2006:20) affirms that, more often families eat together, the less likely kids are to smoke, drink, do drugs, get depressed, develop eating disorders and consider suicide and the more likely they are to do well in school, delay having sex, eat their vegetables, learn big words and know which fork to use - the magic of family meals". The family dinner is not magic on its own but it does creates a consistent time and place where conversation happen, experiences shared and relationships are strengthened. However in Ogoja Education Zone of Cross River State, specifically, unreported cases of drug use/addiction in schools, homes and society abound. The reason for this is the fear of being a victim of

circumstance by the family, police harassment had prevented so many cases to be concealed from teachers and parents. This also notwithstanding, some parents are also deeply involved in drug and see no negative imprint on the child to warrant arrest. In conclusion, adolescents' drug use/addiction and their social adjustment significantly influenced the dimensions of coping with peer pressure, school rules and adult/societal expectations. The lower the level of drug use/addiction, the higher the level of their social adjustment (except in the case of coping with academic pressure where the reverse is the case).

COUNSELING RECOM MEN DAT IONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following major recommendations were made as a guide for counseling implications:

- (1) The National Association of Counseling in Nigeria in collaboration with UNODC, NDLEA and law enforcement agencies should intensify awareness on the negative impact of illicit drug use such as cocaine, heroin or legal substances such as prescription drugs like paracetamol, chloroquin, et cetera. Given the enormous damage narcotics do to humanity, no effort should be spared in curbing this menace.
- (2) The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) should raise the tempo of its effectiveness by investing heavily on technological devices that can enhance its ability to detect drug traffickers or consumers to thwart and frustrate their efforts. Also develop comprehensive strategies in addressing prescription drug use/addiction, support domestic and International investigations targeting organized criminal networks, promote the application of drug control treaties as well as develop practical measures to effectively prevent new psychoactive substances.
- (3) Treatment medications with behavioral therapy are the best way to ensure success for most users/addicts. Treatment approaches should be tailored to each patient's medical, psychiatric and social problems.
- (4) Drug addiction is a preventable disease. Parents should check their children lifestyle in the use of drugs and addiction. An addicted adolescent is one at risk; likewise parental rejection produces more aggressive, frustrating, temper tantrums and destructive addicted children. Parents should socialize their children to normative principles of the society.

REFERENCES

- Afolabi, M. O., Ayilara, A. E., Akinyemi, O. A. & Ola-Olorun, O. J. (2012) "Survey of Drug use Among Young People in Ife, Nigeria". *African Journal of Drug and Alcohol Studies*, 11 (2).
<http://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajdas/articles/view/86622>.
- Aliyu, F. S. (2014). "Drug Abuse and Nigerian Youths", <http://www.dailytrust.com.ng/daily/education/32238-drug-abuse-and-nigerian-outhstbtwkq.HE18-jAmZ.99>.

- Austin, E. W., Pinkleton, B. E. & Fukioka, W. (2000). "The Role of Interpretation Processes and Parental Discussion in the Media's Effects on Adolescents' Use of Alcohol". *Pediatrics*, 105,343-349.
- Berger, K. S. (2001). *The Developing Person, through the Life Span*. 5th ed. New York.
- Boob, G. & Kreek, M. J. (2007). "Stress Dysregulation of Drug Reward Pathways and the Transition to Drug Dependence". *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 164(8), 1149-1159. doi:10.1176/appi.ajp.200705030503.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. "Smoking Attributable Morality, Years of Potential Life Lost, and Productivity Losses". United States 2000-2004. Morbidity and mortality weekly report, <http://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview>. Retrieved 24-02-2016
- Gibbs, N. (2006). "The Magic of the Family Meal". *Issue of the Time Magazine*.
- Isah, A. & Limbeabe, E. U. (2015). *Social Issues at a Glance*. Calabar: Mbome Concern.
- Lynskey, M. T, Health, A. C., Bucholz, K. K., Slutske, W. S., Madden, P. A. F., Nelson, E. C., Statham, D. J. & Martin, N. G. (2003). "Escalation of Drug use in Early onset Cannabis Users Versus Co-twin Controls". *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 289,427-433.
- National Drug Intelligence Centre (2011). *The Economic Impact of Illicit Drug use on American Society*. Washington D. C.: United States . Department of Justice, www.justic.gov/archive/ndic/pubs44
- Obianu, J. J. (2008). *The Effects of Reciprocal Peer Tutoring on the Enhancement of Career Decision making Process among Secondary School Adolescence*. Delta State University, Nigeria.
- Okpo-Ojah (2011). *Nigeria Chronicle*. November 30.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2014). *World drug report*.